

ANALYSIS OF THE TREATMENTS OF FOUNDATION OF THE DAMS OF BELO MONTE HPP

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Abstract. *The Belo Monte HPP has 36 dams / dikes built under the most diverse types of foundations - sandstone (graben region), thick alluvial terraces, residual soils with canaliculi and fractured rocks among others.*

This article will introduce a summary of the characteristics of the main foundation types of the dams at the Belo Monte HPP, as well as a summary of the treatments used and the results obtained after two years of reservoir filling.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Belo Monte hydroelectric complex has been built on the Xingu River, in the Municipalities of Altamira and Vitória do Xingu, in the State of Pará. When fully built in 2020, it will have a nominal installed capacity of 11,233.1 MW and will be the fourth largest hydroelectric plant of the world in installed capacity, with twenty-four generating units, of which 06 Bulb-generating units with 233.1 MW in the Pimental site and eighteen Francis units (11,000 MW) in the Belo Monte Site.

The general arrangement of the Belo Monte hydroelectric complex, a run-of-river hydroelectric power plant that had as its conception the exploitation of the great natural desniveness existing in the "Volta Grande" stretch of the Xingu River, is characterized as one of the largest bypass plant in the world for it presents distinct and distant sites among themselves, from the structures of the Pimental site on the Xingu River, which is approximately 7 km long, to the Belo Monte site, where the main Power House of the project is under construction, on the river bank, reaching a maximum abrupt fall of 94.12 m.

These two sites are approximately 40 km away from each other and are interconnected by the largest Power Canal ever built in the world (For more details, see Ref. [1]), approximately 16 km long and 0.3 km wide, and by the Intermediate Reservoir, an artificial reservoir bordered by 27 dikes, most of them of large capacity, like Dique 13, approximately 2000 m long, 53 m high and 5,7 thousand m³, as well as a few small dikes, such as Dike 1, 80 m long, 6 m height and 5 thousand m³ volume (See Picture 1).

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Figure 1 – General Arrangement of HPP Belo Monte

This paper presents the main types of foundations found in the Belo Monte HPP and the main treatments used in them, giving greater detail in the characterization and treatment of the rock mass in the foundation of the Power Intake of the Belo Monte site.

2 FOUNDATIONS IN RESIDUAL SOILS OF MIGMATITO

Residual soils of migmatites, predominant lithology at the three sites of the Belo Monte HPP, are present on the foundations of almost all land works and were the main source of embankment material for the construction of the dams and the dikes.

During the excavation of the first exploratory trenches, the presence of areas with a great concentration of tubular cavities (canaliculi) of subcentimetric to decimetric diameters was found in the foundation of the dikes, in residual soil of migmatite. These canaliculi present sub-vertical development, reaching more than 6m depth and lateral interconnections in the places where they are concentrated, promoting a significant increase of the permeability of the foundation, as demonstrated by the investigations and innumerable in situ permeability tests carried out in Dikes 19B and 28 (Figure 2).

Picture 2 - Macro-canaliculi at exploratory trench of Dike 19B

The infiltration tests in the wells indicated "k" permeability values of the order of 10-4 cm/s for the residual soil of migmatite, however, the presence of canaliculi concentrations led the designer to adopt larger permeabilities, 10-3 cm/s, both for the homogeneous upper layer of the foundation, corresponding to the mature residual soil, and to the lower soil layer, which preserves the structure and texture of the matrix rock.

Figure 3 - Schematic section of the canaliculi treatments in the foundation of the Dams and Dikes

The following measures were adopted in the treatments of the canaliculi:

- Execution of an exploratory trench, with depth of 3m and fine cleaning with air jet execution, to enable the verification of the presence of micro-canaliculi (millimetric diameter) and macro-canaliculi (centimetric to decimetric diameter);
- When found canaliculi in the foundation, the excavation of the trench was deepened by a further 3 m, totaling 6 m depth;
- In the regions of points 2 and 3 indicated in Figure 3, the canaliculi with a diameter ≥ 20 mm were obturated, with a cement grout with a factor of 0.7: 1.0 (a:c).
- In the region indicated in point 2 of Figure 3, sand filter layer (blind drain) was executed, 0.75 m wide (horizontal), compacted with CR $\geq 65\%$, in contact with the downstream wall of the trench, to dilute the possible elevated gradients in the canaliculi.

Soon after the filling, were observed resurgences on the downstream of some dikes, as well as rapid response in some of the instruments installed on the foundations of the dikes and dams, with some cases of artesianism, particularly in the region of the abutments (see Figure 4), such as Dike 7B. In this dike it was possible to observe water outcrops in some canaliculi located on the surface of the ground downstream, besides the finding of artesianism in the piezometers installed in the left abutments, indicating that the deeper layers were more permeable than the surface ones (see Figure 5).

Figure 4 - Downstream resurgences

The solution adopted by the designer to combat the high water flow of and hydraulic gradient with the potential to generate carriages of soil particles on the downstream of these structures, was the execution of an inverted filter, delimited by a maximum

hydraulic gradient of 15% in the foundation. However, where the piezometers showed high gradients, the execution of this inverted filter protection was extended beyond the area delimited in design.

It should be noted that the water outcrops downstream, in general, did not compromise the safety of the structures, while the execution of the inverted filters ensured the safety of these structures over time against the possibility of piping.

It is also important to note that in most of the dikes, some with up to 60m in height, the piezometry revealed a normal behavior with neutral pressures lower than the control values predicted in the project. Flows recorded by flow meters are particularly affected by periods of rain and drought. The specific flows per meter of structure have been $Q_{esp} < 1.80 \text{ l/min/m}$ (control value: $Q_{esp} < 2.0 \text{ l/min/m}$), considered within normality.

Figure 5 - Occurrence of artesianism downstream of Dike 7B.

3 FOUNDATION ON RESIDUAL SOILS OF SANDSTONE

Along a 3 km extension of the Intermediate Reservoir, located between dikes 6C and 8A, the Xingu Complex stratigraphic unit, represented in the region by the migmatites, which supports the relief of the right divisor of the reservoir, is interrupted by a geological structure limited by normal faults, which constitutes a tectonic fossa filled by predominantly sandy sediments, correlated to the Trombetas Formation of the Sedimentary Basin of Amazonas. This region of the divisor, which is characterized by a flattened relief, formed by an elongated spike shaped in sandstone, above the elevation 130m, is called Graben of the Macacão (Great Monkey Graben - see Figure 6).

Figure 6 - Schematic section of the Graben on the site of the Dikes

Three dikes interfere with the Graben, partly the dikes 6C (on the right abutment) and 8A (on the left abutment) and fully the dike 8B, all with foundation in sandstone residual soil and the last with a stretch founded on residual soil of diamictite (sediment with lamitic matrix and blocks of migmatite), wich presents characteristics of permeability and resistance similar to the residual soil of migmatite.

The characteristic feature of the foundations in these dikes is the occurrence of residual sandstone soil consisting of silty fine sand, yellowish-white, fluffy to medium-compact and with permeability varying between 10-5 cm/s and 10-3 cm/s in the upper 8m to 12m of the profile, passing below to compact and very compact, up to the bedrock, of coherence C4 (friable rock) or higher (corresponding to the SPT value >3/1 strokes/cm (see Figures 7 and 8).

Figure 7 - Dike 8B - Friable sandstone

Figure 8 - Dike 8B - Exploratory Trench

For a better characterization of the foundations, at this stage of the design, a quite comprehensive investigations campaign was carried out, with the execution of more than 3,200m of drill holes on these foundations in addition to about 2,400m of vertical and inclined drilling in the stretch of the spike between dikes 6C and 8B, which functions as a dam with 2.6km long, and whose objective was the knowledge of the stratigraphy of the sandstone package and its permeability and erodibility.

The best geological-geotechnical knowledge of the foundations showed the need for a greater percolation control, due to the great erodibility and permeability of the materials present, and the solution adopted in the final design was the treatment by cut-off excavation until intercept the sandstone horizon with C4 coherence, which has permeability $\leq 1 \times 10^{-4}$ cm/s. At the downstream of the dike, along its entire length, a large inverted filter has been built, complemented by a line of relief wells implanted at the downstream slope, spaced 12m and 15m deep (See Figure 9)

As shown in Figure 10, the piezometers located at the foundation showed a rapid response, however there was no record of water outcrop or artesianism in the inverted filter downstream of the dike. The specific flow measured by the MV-2 (totalizer), further downstream, is of the order of 2.5 l/min/m, > 2.0 l/min/m, but it is the Graben region, with foundation in more permeable sandstone.

Figure 9 - Dike 8A - Scheme of the foundation treatments in sandstone in the Graben region

Figure 10 - Piezometric levels of section 3 of 8B Dike

4 ROCK FOUNDATION ON MIGMATITO

Among the structures built on a rock foundation, it is worth noting the main site of the Power Intake - Power House deployed in the Belo Monte site, with a rock excavation height of 80m, for which it was extremely important the structural characterization of the main discontinuities families that cut the rock mass of the foundation, aiming at the stability studies of the Power Intake and the orientation of the deep foundation treatment.

The structures are located on the edge of the Sedimentary Basin of the Amazon, and founded in migmatite of the crystalline basement, belonging to the stratigraphic unit Complex Xingu. Regarding the structural aspects of the basement in this area, both the

drill holes and the mappings carried out showed a rock mass, generally, little fractured, cut by well-spaced transcurrent faults, represented by milonites and very fractured cataclasites of metrical thickness and extension of up to hundreds of meters.

The fracture pattern of the rock mass in the Power Intake area was interpreted from the measurements carried out in the oriented cores of the drill holes executed at various phases of design and, later, in the structural surveys carried out on the slopes of the excavations, analyzed in the poles frequency stereograms. The analysis of the stereogram prepared with all measurements performed, as presented in Figure 11, shows the occurrence of a main family of sub-horizontal joints with a dip of up to 20 °, called S1, which represent relief joints, followed by three others families, also relevant, of joints sub-verticals NW, ENE and NS-NNW, respectively named S2, S3 and S5.

Figure 11 – Power Intake - Stereogram of Frequency of Poles – Drill holes and Surface Mapping Data (the axis of the Power Intake is approximately EW).

Among these main families of joints that compartmentalize the rock mass, the subverticals discontinuities, together with the very fractured bands of cataclasites, play an important role in the establishment of the natural ways of percolation of the water in the mass rock. This is because they cross at different depths, both the persistent sub-horizontal relief joints, as well as the medium slope and the random joints, of lesser expression and persistence, providing the interconnection of the open discontinuities, which guided the inclination of the grout curtain with the purpose of intercepting them.

The Power Intake was founded on sound migmatite to moderately weathered (A1/A2), whose top presents slight inclination between the elevations 28.00m on the left hydraulic side and 42.00m on the right side. The drainage system of the rock mass has a drainage gallery embedded in the concrete structure of the Power Intake, with variable elevation floor, in steps, following the topographic conformation of the foundation of the structure and with a tunnel of drainage of 3m high excavated in the rock mass, with floor in the elevation 16.00m (See Figure 12).

Figure 12 - Instrumented section of Block 4 of the Power Intake

Figure 13 - Instrumented section of the main Powerhouse

In order to control the uplifts and flow by the foundation of the Power Intake, a grout curtain with a spacing of 3m between the holes was executed from the drainage gallery, inclined 15 ° to upstream with the objective of intercepting the system of sub vertical joints until the elevation 11.00 m and a curtain of 4 "vertical drains, also spaced 3m, connecting it to the lower drainage tunnel by gravity.

The results of the groutings carried out in the generation 1 and 2 circuits showed low absorption of cement grout with only 6 holes with absorption greater than 100 kg/m and another 8 holes with absorptions greater than 35 kg/m, out of a total of 212 holes between exploratory, primary, secondary and tertiary (including 2 quaternary holes).

The grout takes above 100 kg/m occurred in the blocks TA-06, (reaching 1595 kg/m in hole S-21), TA-08, Central Wall, TA-10, TA-15 (reaching 900kg/m in hole S-48) and TA-16, in general, in stretches of lengths between 18m and 31m, certainly with greater contribution of subvertical permeable fractures, associated to the relief joints.

The Figures 12 and 13 show respectively the typical instrumented sections of the Belo Monte Site's Power Intake and Powerhouse. In general, the instruments have performed well, allowing the evaluation of the performance of these structures and the comparison with the control values predicted in the design.

The response of all piezometers to the filling of the reservoir was quick. The piezometric levels reached a maximum peak, close to the deadline of the filling and, afterwards, show a downward tendency of the subpressions, as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14 – Piezometric readings of the Power Intake’s Central Block

It is important to note that after two years of reservoir filling; most of the drains that connect the drainage gallery with the drainage tunnel were colmated by carbonation. However, shortly after the unobstruction of the same, it was not possible to observe a relief of the subpressions, reflected in the instrumentation.

The flow meters have also indicated a good performance of the foundation, since the values observed after two years of filling are lower than the specific reference flow, of 2 l/m/m, as observed in Table 1.

Table 1 - Flow readings in the Drain Tunnel of the Power Intake

Weir Gauge	Date	Flow (l/s)	Flow (l/min)	drained length (m)	Q espec. (l/min/m)
MV-1	04/01/18	4,17	250,14	680	0,75
MV-2	04/01/18	4,39	263,37		

In terms of displacements observed in the triortogonal meters, these values are well below those of other works, indicating the efficiency of the treatments and competence of the foundation, according to Table 2.

Table 2 - Comparison of the displacements of the structures

RCC Dam	Maximum differential displacement (mm)			
	Joint Opening	Differential Displacement	Horizontal Sliding	
			Foundation	Crest
Sítio Belo Monte	1,45	0,60	0,88	-
Sítio Pimental	0,43	0,28	0,50	-
Dona Francisca	2,30	0,75	3,40	-
Monte Claro	1,30	1,20	1,40	3,10
Castro Alves	4,10	0,50	1,50	3,05
14 de Julho	2,00	1,25	1,00	-
Canoas I	3,36	1,65	1,35	-
Canoas II	1,25	0,65	0,35	-
Arvoredo	1,20	1,30	2,00	-

5 CONCLUSION

In general, the treatments used in the foundations of the structures of Belo Monte HPP presented a good result.

The foundations of dams and dikes based on migmatite residual soils, had a relatively high permeability (10-3 cm/s), but not very different from those found in the permeability tests carried out in the study phase of the final design.

As presented in item 2, there was a need for punctual surges treatments with inverted filters, which were not initially foreseen in the basic design, however is considered that this post-fill treatment is more efficient and economical, since it treats the foundation at the exact point of the flow outcrop, avoiding the coverage of large area with inverted filter.

On the other hand, the foundation of the dikes built on sandstone residual soils in the Graben region, which initially caused great concerns about their high permeability and erodibility, show no anomaly after two years of filling, demonstrating a good efficiency of the treatments used in the foundation, by means of cut off supported on the C4 coherence sandstone.

The treatments of the rock foundations, especially in the Power Intake and Powerhouse of the site Belo Monte presented an excellent performance, with very low values registered in the triortogonal meters and flow meters, pointing out the efficiency of the treatments used, as well as the foundation rock competency of these structures.

Thus, the treatments used in the foundations of HPP Belo Monte were considered satisfactory and it may be recommended that they be used for similar foundations of other works.

6 REFERENCES

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